

Impact of Social Media on Teenager

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Abstract:- In light of how quickly technology is developing in the modern era, social media use and its influence have become a significant source of concern. So, is social media influencing people and society in a positive way? Due to the introduction of Will teenagers who are particularly vulnerable and have access to the Internet in a large number of homes benefit from social media's widespread use? Social media is more detrimental to teenagers than helpful. The main focus of this article is how social media affects teenagers. This article seeks to reflect the advantages and disadvantages of social media for teenagers in a more impartial and understandable manner, drawing from a variety of websites and articles.

Keywords:- Impact of Social Media , Postive Impact and Negative Impact of Social Media.

I. INTRODUCTION

Social media sites like Facebook, Instagram, YouTube, and Twitter are used by people of all ages for networking and communication, and Indians spend about 2.4 hours each day on social media alone. The fact that young people between the ages of 13-19 spend so much time on these apps—Facebook and Instagram alone have 97.2 million and 69 million users from this age bracket in India, respectively—clearly demonstrates a rising dependence on social media. Constant use exposes users to harmful content, alters behaviour patterns, makes them feel inferior, and can even lead to cyberbullying. Social media has various noble objectives, like promoting intercultural connections, uncovering pertinent content, and providing non-stop entertainment. However, constant scrolling could also be detrimental. According to studies, young individual who use social media are three time more likely to feel depression, putting a large portion of the population at risk for suicidal thoughts and deeds.

A. Positive Impact of Social Media on Teenagers

➤ Encourages Social Interaction

Social networking sites are primarily used to help people socialize with each other, regardless of barriers like distance. Positive effects on relationships are possible. By communicating frequently and sharing their experiences online, young people can establish new friendships and keep those they already have. Social media can provide a virtual alternative for teenagers who find it difficult to connect with others in the real world and keep them from feeling alone.

➤ Advantages for Mental Health

Using social media increases the release of oxytocin, which lowers stress and increases feelings of joy. Online interactions are frequently less demanding and call for little to no emotion than in-person socializing. Likes and encouraging remarks frequently result in rewards and happiness that require very little time or effort to achieve. Of course, it could be harmful to mental health if the comments are unfavourable or the number of likes is thought to be too low. Facebook is planning to follow Instagram's lead, which recently made the number of likes on a post visible only to the profile owner in response to user feedback. This helps to address the issue of teenagers (and people in general).

➤ Offers Chances For Learning

Youngsters can read blogs, watch videos, and view images—all of which have educational value. Social networking sites can serve as a foundation for research and fact-finding projects, as well as a forum for discussing homework and assignment subjects.

B. Negative Impact of Social Media on Teenagers

➤ Online Harassment

Cyberbullying is when someone or a group is targeted by technology with the goal of causing them emotional, psychological, or physical harm. A child should get help right away if they are the target of cyberbullying.

➤ May Jeopardize Security

Regrettably, social media gives predators a place to lure in and mistreat kids. Users have the ability to make false profiles, putting kids in danger of interacting with strangers who could hurt them. On social media, kids should never give out their location or personal information to strangers. Teenager should keep their account private.

➤ Ill-Focused

Distractions can also come from social media. It may take focus away from something your child should be doing, like studying, practicing a sport, or doing an assignment. Make sure your kids are engaging in social activities and leading a healthy lifestyle away from electronics and computers. It's also a good idea to keep an eye on social media usage online and remove electronics from bedroom.

C. Objectives of Study –

- To Understand the purpose of using the social media of teenagers .
- To study the influence of social media on teenagers .
- To study the positive impact of social media on teenagers.

- To study the negative impact of social media on teenagers.
- To offer suggestions to teenager to use social media on a right way.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

➤ *Bradawy and Hashem (2015)*

In order to determine whether or not students' use of social media affects their academic performance, Bradawy and Hashem (2015) conducted a study. The study found no evidence of a connection between social media use and students' academic performance.

https://scholar.google.co.in/scholar?q=related:DGkdkx4pDY0J:scholar.google.com/&scioq=Badawy+and+Hashem+study+on+impact+on+social+media+on+teenager&hl=en&as_sdt=0,5&as_vis=1#d=gs_qabs&t=1698428525292&u=%23p%3DDGkdkx4pDY0J.

➤ *Peter (2015)*

Scholars'. In order to complete his studies for his bachelor's degree in education administration, Peter (2015) studied at Lagos University. The study's goal was to investigate the relationship between University of Lagos students' academic performance and social media use. The results of this study indicate that a sizable portion of University of Lagos students suffer from social media addiction. The researcher recommended that social media be used for educational purposes as well; additionally, the researcher recommended social networking.

[https://www.academia.edu/download/36928369/SOCI AL_MEDIA_AND_ACADEMIC_PERFORMANCE_OF_T HE_STUDENTS_IN_UNIVERSITY_OF_LAGOS.pdf](https://www.academia.edu/download/36928369/SOCI_AL_MEDIA_AND_ACADEMIC_PERFORMANCE_OF_T HE_STUDENTS_IN_UNIVERSITY_OF_LAGOS.pdf)

➤ *Jenna Christofferson Palermo 2016*

Today's most frequent users of social networking sites are teenagers (SNS). Young people today are growing up in a cultural context where social media will play a major role in mediating many aspects of their lives and shaping many of their opportunities and experiences. Consequently, given how ingrained social media is in adolescents' lives, debates and questions concerning its impact on their development arise. Information regarding the impact of SNS on the social and emotional development of teenagers was gathered through a systematic review of fifteen publications. According to the studies gathered, using SNS can have positive and negative effects on a teen's social and emotional development. https://ir.stthomas.edu/ssw_mstrp/593/

➤ *Child and Family Studies Journal (2018, Edition).*

Adolescents have a tendency to associate with a demographic that is particularly vulnerable to the negative psychological and behavioural effects of social media use. Given that teenagers' behaviour is easily influenced by the social context in which they live, parents and friends are probably the most important individuals who have a significant impact on the behavioural outcomes that result from teens' use of social media. This study attempts to

investigate the association between teenagers' propensity for social comparison and envy and the level of social media use, in light of worries about the harmful effects of teen social media use. Using a snowball sampling technique, survey information from 250 teenagers was obtained. A partial least-squares regression's findings revealed that teenagers whose parents compared their offspring to other teenagers in a peer group that was marked by intense intragroup competition had a significantly stronger positive relationship between the intensity of their social media use and envy. However, only teenagers who belong to a peer group that has a high level of in-group competition showed a significant positive relationship between the intensity of their social media use and social comparison. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10826-017-0872-8>

➤ *Kari Word, Hajeen Choi, and Vanessa P. Dennen*

- *Research and Development in Educational Technology* 68, 1635-1658, 2020

The research fields that have examined social media's relationship to education and, more generally, its use by high school and college students are examined in this scoping review. The sample looks at research conducted between 2009 and 2018. 580 pertinent peer-reviewed articles published through the end of 2018 were found using a Web of Science search; 260 (44.8%) of these articles had an educational focus. Ever since relevant social media articles first appeared in 2009, research in this field has been steadily increasing. Approximately 50% of this study was carried out. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11423-020-09796-z>

➤ *Research Hypothesis :*

- Ha1: Teenagers spent more time on social media networking sites
- Ha0: Teenagers does not spent more time on social media networking sites
- Hb1: Social media has positive impact on teenager
- Hb0: Social media has negative impact on teenager

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research is conducted by primary data through the method of questions and second data from various sources like website.

➤ *Primary Data*

The primary data has been obtained from the selected group of population (between 13 -19 age group) with the help of questionnaire.

• *Sampling Decisions:*

Sampling can be defined as the art of drawing the samples from.

• *Sample Size:*

Appropriate number of sample size (i.e., 150) was put to use for the purpose of collecting primary data from the teenager.

Sampling Method:

Non- probability sampling design bases on convenient sampling method has been used for this research study.

Secondary Data:

The secondary data has been obtained from published as well as unpublished literature .On the topic and from Journals, Research Articles, Thesis, Websites.

Techniques of Data Analysis:

The collected information and primary DATA have been subjected to DATA analysis and interpretation. The collected primary DATA has been preceded considering the designing of the structured and non-disguised questionnaire. After being carefully examined, revised, and verified, the primary data was then presented as data, charts, graphs, and diagrams, as appropriate.

Limitations of the Study:

- As it is a recent topic, not much research papers are there for the purpose of references.
- Some of the respondents did not respond to the questions carefully.
- Impact of social media on teenager is a huge concept in itself, 150 respondents won't preview the complete picture.
- The study is limited because the researcher does not have enough research material.
- Since the researcher must juggle the study with other academic obligations and exams, the time allotted for the study does not allow for broader coverage.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Showing the Age of Respondents

Fig 1 Age of Respondents

Table 1 Age of Respondents

YEAR	PERCENTAGE
13-15 years	26%
15-17 years	38.7%
17-19 years	35.3

Interpretation:

- ✓ In the above table we can see that 26% of respondents are between the age of 13- 15 years ,35.3% of respondents are between the age of 17-19 years.
- ✓ Majority of respondents that is 38.7% are between the age of 15-17 year.

Showing the Mostly used Social Media by Respondents.

Fig 2 Social Media by Respondents

Table 2 Social Media by Respondents

SOCIAL MEDIA (APP)	PERCENTAGE
YouTube	83.5%
Facebook	58%
WhatsApp	73.3%
Snapchat	50%
Instagram	63.7%

Interpretation

In the above table majority of respondents that 83.5% of respondents uses YouTube. 58% of respondents uses Facebook,73.3% of respondents uses WhatsApp,50% of respondents uses Snapchat, and 63.7% uses Instagram.

Showing the Mostly used Social Media by Respondents.

Fig 3 Social Media by Respondents

Table 3 Social Media by Respondents

HOURS	PERCENTAGE
1	25.3%
2-3	36%
3-5	22%
5 and above	16.7%

• Interpretation

In the above table it shows that how many hours teenager spend on social media most of them i.e.36% spend 2 to 3 hours on social media.25.3% spend hours on social media.22% spend 3-5 hours.16.7% spend 5 hours on social media.

• Showing Post on Social Media

Fig 4 Post on Social Media

Table 4 Post on Social Media

POST	PERCENTAGE
Very often	36.7%
Sometimes	43.3%
Rarely	20%

• Interpretation

In the above table it shows that how often teenager post on social media 36.7% are very often in Posting on social media. Majority of respondents i.e.43.3%post on social media .20% rarely post on social media.

• Showing is Social Media First Things to Check in the Morning

Fig 5 Social Media First Things to Check in the Morning

Table 5 Social Media First Things to Check in the Morning

RESPONSE	PERCENTAGE
Yes	35.3%
No	43.3%
Sometimes	21.3%

• Interpretation

In the above table it showing that how many teenager check social media Frist in the morning. Majority of respondents response i.e.43.3%said no they don't check it .35.3% response yes and 21.3% response some time in the morning

• Showing of using Social Media

Fig 6 Social Media

Table no 6 Social Media

Purpose	Percentage
To find information	29.3%
Chatting with friends and relatives	40.7%
To share video and pictures	16%
Other	14%

• Interpretation

In the above it showing the purpose of using social media. Majority of respondents i.e.40.7% respond to chat with friends and relatives.29.3% to find information.16 % used to share video and pictures.14% used for the purpose of other.

• Showing the useful or Not for Learning

Fig 7 Not for Learning

Table 7 Not for Learning

RESPONSE	PERCENTAGE
Very useful	34%
Sometimes	52%
Not useful	14%

• Interpretation

In the above table it showing that Social media useful or not in learning. Majority of respondents respond i.e.52% are sometimes.34% respond very useful.14% no useful in learning.

• Showing the Experience of Anxiety

Fig 8 Experience of Anxiety

Table 8 Experience of Anxiety

Anxiety experience	Percentage
Yes	30.7%
No	45.3%
Maybe	24%

• Interpretation

In the above table it showing that majority of respondents that is 45.3% doesn't face anxiety.30.7% experience anxiety.24% does not experience anxiety.

IV. CONCLUSION

Teens who use social media have some psychological and physical advantages, but overall, the benefits outweigh the drawbacks. We must use social media responsibly and with reason. Help teens grow by using it as a tool rather than a weapon. While most problems are impossible to fully solve, people can still come up with some solutions We can use social networks to get involved in issues. Research content using problematic social networks is more concentrated on the following, according to internal and external research literature:

- Describing the psychological and behavioural relationships between variables and using problematic social networks;
- Examining the detrimental effects of social networking problems on the psychological development of adolescents; and

- Elucidating the systemic mechanism of problematic social networks.

FINDING

Teens' mental health and general well-being are impacted by social media in both positive and negative ways. Teens who use social media platforms to stay in touch with friends and family and feel connected can benefit from it, but they can also experience loneliness, depression, anxiety, and FOMO (fear of missing out).

SCOPE OF STUDY

The goal of the study is to determine how social media usage among teenagers people affects changes in behaviour.

Though this study will only focus on Indian teenager, it acknowledges that new interactive technologies have an impact on age groups beyond the teenager demographic. The research is how teenager thought about technology and impact on social media on their life. The researchers can also include the thought about parents concern during to increase technology

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APPENDIX

- **Age**
 - 13-15
 - 15-17
 - 17-19
- **Class**
 - 8-9
 - 9-10
 - 10-12

- *Which Social Media Platforms you Mostly Everyday Day?*
 - YouTube
 - Facebook
 - WhatsApp
 - Snapchat
 - Instagram.
- *How many Hours do you Spend on Social Media Everyday Day?*
 - 1 hours
 - 2 -3 hours
 - 3- 5 hours
 - 5 and above
- *How Often do you Post on Social Media?*
 - Very often
 - Sometimes
 - Rarely
- *Is Social Media is the First Thing you Check in the Morning?*
 - Yes
 - No
 - Sometimes
- *What is the Purpose of using Social Media ?*
 - To find information
 - chatting with friends and relatives
 - To share video and pictures
 - Other
- *How Useful is Social Media for Learning ?*
 - Very useful
 - Sometimes
 - Not useful
- *Do you Experience Any form of Anxiety while using Social Media Platform ?*
 - Yes
 - No
 - Maybe
- *Do you Feel Social Media has Positive Effect on Teenager ?*
 - Yes
 - No
 - May be
- *Do you Feel Peers Pressure in Social Media?*
 - Yes
 - No
 - Sometimes
- *Do you Think Social Media Helps to Connect to World ?*
 - Yes
 - No
 - Maybe
- *How Often do you use Chat App on Social Media Accounts ?*
 - Very often
 - Moderate
 - Never
- *How many Social Media Sites do you Actively used?*
 - 1
 - 2
 - More than 3
- *Social Media Reducing the Time of Sleep you Get?*
 - Agree
 - Disagree
- *Social Media is a New Platform to Build Career for Teenagers?*
 - Agree
 - Disagree
- *Is Social Media is Also a Earning Source?*
 - Agree
 - Disagree